

Management of Monetary Policy in Macro-Economic Stability in Nigeria: Islamist Perspectives

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Abstract

The main goals of monetary is to stabilize macro-economic growth, curb unemployment and protect the value of the currency in a polity. The relative significance of monetary policy has become a matter of debate between economists. While some argue that the monetary policy has a great impact on economic activities, others contend that the fiscal policy is more effective. The challenge of monetary and fiscal policy has engendered a dilemma that has remained unresolved in spite of manifold ideologies. With the aid of descriptive research design using literature reviewed, the study interrogated the dichotomy, examined both polices within the framework of Islamic orthodoxy and attempt reconciliation between the opposing views. The paper found out that apart from the fact that both policies failed to maintain macro-economic stability, there is a gap between the injunctions of Islam and the system of operation in monetary and fiscal policies in Nigeria. The paper concluded that both policies can proffer macro-economic stability with the by adopting prophetic recommendations and engaging in removal of lending interest rate, wasteful consumption and utilization of diversified economy.

Keywords: Management, macro-economic, monetary policy, stability, Islamist perspective

Introduction

Poverty (*Faqru*) is fiercely raging in Nigeria, a nation of over 200 million people and the most densely populated black nation on earth. Human poverty in Islam is indeed concerned with both material as well as cultural and spiritual poverty. Society in Islam is for the individual who is accountable to Allah for his action.¹ The Nigerian Labour Force Survey (NLFS) puts Nigeria's unemployment rate at 4.1 percent in the first quarter of 2023² while the National Bureau of Statistics also postulates that the country's inflation rate is at 24.08 percent within the same year.³ It was this phenomenon that instigates Allinson to have said: "It is not the fall of petroleum price in the world market as such that has brought untold hardship and sadness. It is the ineptitude and inability of our management team to adjust to the challenges of modern times."⁴

The import of the above assertion is a reflection of demoralized, disoriented and disorganized public service in Nigeria. It also epitomized the shambles in the economy and the dire need of a viable and effective management team that can revive the deteriorating state of affairs in economy. The Nigerian currency, Naira has faced persistent depreciation with nearly 75 percent. The Central Bank of Nigeria disclosed that Nigeria has external debt of 33.24 trillion and domestic debt 54.13 trillion with a deficit of \$2.3 trillion.⁵ This situation has accelerated poverty in Nigeria with 63 percent (133 million) Nigerians living in multidimensional poverty.⁶

This state of economic phenomenon metamorphosed Nigeria society where criminality is a recognized means of livelihood for the youth, access to education and health care is curtailed by financial incapacity and the gap between the have and have not has become a chasm. It is against this background that Nigeria has implemented various monetary and fiscal policies in responses to different economic challenges. While the application of both policies under different poverty alleviation measures introduced by different government such as Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in the early 1980 till 2021 and adopted 2021-2025 National Development Plan, has become a controversial issue.

This phenomenon has generated confliction of perspectives among economists and scholars. Unimpressive performance of both monetary and fiscal policy has been adduced to be responsible for the status quo. Some scholars such as Adeniyi *et al* argued that monetary policy has a great impact on economic activity⁷ while Ogunbiyi and Okoye contended that fiscal policy is more effective.⁸ Okorie *et al* in their own submissions maintained an intermediary position that both are effective in stimulating economic growth.⁹

However, irrespective of different findings from various investigations, on whether monetary or fiscal policy is more effective in a particular economy at a time, the employment of these polices in Nigeria since independence has not significantly improved the financial and banking sector. Therefore, the motivation of this study is derived from various studies on the Nigeria macro-economy that have engendered an unresolved dilemma. The paper interrogates the dichotomy, examines both policies within the framework of Islamic orthodoxy and attempt reconciliation with the opposing views. In accomplishing these goals, the following subheadings are slated thus: conceptual clarification of relevant terms in monetary and fiscal policies in Nigeria, interaction between both policies, interrogation of the dichotomy between them; management of both policies within the framework of Islamic orthodoxy and concluded with findings, recommendation and conclusion.

Conceptual Clarifications

It is not a gainsaying that Nigeria has faced varieties of economic challenges, over the years, in spite of different government measures to curb it through changing from monetary policy to fiscal policy. It is quite pertinent here to briefly analyze both terminologies. Hilbers (2005) at an IMF Seminar defines monetary policy as the central bank's control of the available ability of credit in the economy to achieve broad objectives of economic policy. He sees fiscal policy refers to the government's choice regarding the use of taxation and government spending to regulate the aggregate level of economic activity.¹⁰ In the perspective of Goshut and Landi (2014), monetary policy is the part of economic policy which regulates the level of money or liquidity in the economy in order to control inflation while fiscal policy is the part of government policy concerning the raising of revenue through taxation and other means and deciding on the pattern of expenditure to attain some desirable macro-economic goals.¹¹

From the foregoing, we can infer that while monetary policy connotes the combination of measures designed to regulate the value, supply and cost of money in the economy, the fiscal policy denotes the use of government revenue and expenditure policy to influence the level of economic activity. However, both policies aimed at combating unemployment and other macro-economic variables to ensure a sustainable level of economic growth and development.¹²

In Islam, Mannan opines that monetary policy is expected to pursue the goal of maintaining stability in the value of money, economic well-being, full employment, optimum economic growth and promotion of distributive justice. As he noted, Islam views money as a medium of exchange not as a commodity while fiscal policy is expected to perform the function of allocation, distribution and stabilization arising out of value orientation, ethical, and social dimension in public income and expenditure.¹³ The Fiscal Policy in Islam ceases to be neutral and is expected to explain the situation not merely as they are but as they ought to be. Thus, the process of allocating resources used between private and social goods, the adjustment of the distribution of earning, the redistribution of existing income and wealth and the use of budgeting policy as an instrument of price stability must provide a clear manifestation of social and moral concern.¹⁴

Interaction between Monetary and Fiscal Policy in Managing Macro-Economic Growth in Nigeria

The objectives of monetary and fiscal policy in Nigeria are wide-ranging but both policies aim at achieving relative macro-economic stability. These objectives according to Mosa *et al* (2013) include increase in Gross Domestic Product (GDP), growth rate, improvement in the balance of payment and so

on.¹⁵ Effectiveness of both monetary and fiscal policy have been a major concern to economist and policy makers with advocacy ranging from fiscalists, monetarists and both policy coordinations.¹⁶

In the history of Nigeria economy, monetary policy has been combined and remained dominant against fiscal policy from the First Republic (1960-1966) to the last part of the Third Republic (1983-1985) while fiscal policy was adopted in the Third Republic, it undermined the efficacy of monetary policy till date.¹⁷ This means there has been a shift from direct control to indirect control of the challenge of unemployment. It is in this regard that Muhammed (2012) postulated a need to finetune the fiscal policy to be more effective in addressing unemployment menace.¹⁸

Furthermore, in the view of Subair (2006), the inability of the monetary authority in the First Republic to ascertain the amount of money in circulation precisely renders the monetary policy ineffective.¹⁹ This was attributed to poor record keeping, the activities of money doubters, the emergencies of fake currencies and the habit of hoarding money. These constraints as Subair concluded triggered the loss of the control of money supply through open market operations, special deposit, liquidity ratio, bank rate and so on.²⁰ In this regard, the following table reflects the implication of monetary policy on unemployment rate under macro-economic from 1966 to 1985 in Nigeria.²¹

Unemployment Rate from 1966 to 1985 in Nigeria

Year	Labour Force (In Million)	Gainfully Occupied Person (In Million)	Unemployed Persons	Unemployment Rate in Labour Force (In Percentage)
1966	23.81	23.42	0.40	1.69
1970	26.08	24.05	2.03	7.80
1974	28.56	27.31	1.25	4.40
1975	29.56	27.91	1.31	4.50
1980	32.74	31.76	0.98	3.00
1985	36.05	34.60	1.45	4.00

Source: Federal Office of Statistics Labour Force Sample Survey (Preliminary Report) Dec.1983.

The import of the above table revealed the impact of monetary policy on unemployment menace between the first and second republic which rise and fall due to the aforementioned factors. It is undisputable fact that both monetary and fiscal policy variables have a dominant effect on economic activity and real GDP and inflation in Nigeria but the impact of the policies depend on the policy variable selected. While some policy variables are considered to be more beneficial to the social and economic development.²² According to Yakubu *et al*, the relative impact of fiscal and monetary policy has been studied in many literatures. He enumerated scholars who support monetarist view who asserts that monetary policy generally has a greater impact on economic growth and dominate fiscal policy in cases of its impacts on investment and growth.²³ These scholars include Ajayi (1974),²⁴ Elli`ot (1975),²⁵ Battern and Hafer (1983).²⁶

Some scholars such as Chawdhing,²⁷ Olaloye and Ikhide²⁸ contended that those fiscal policy stimulants are crucial for economic growth. Other scholars such as Okorie *et al* (2017) maintained an intermediary position that both monetary and fiscal policy has positive effect on income and they are important tools, for stimulating economic growth and development in Nigeria based on the research conducted between 1981-2012.²⁹ Nwoko *et al* also corroborated Okorie *et al* on their perspectives but opined that the effectiveness depends on factors other than the amount in circulation and while the Central Bank need to look for alternative strategies to promote economic growth.³⁰

Furthermore, Ayodeji and Oluwole assert that monetary policy effectiveness is limited and need additional policy.³¹ In the findings of Chuku, both policies had interacted in a counteractive manner for most of the 1980-1994. He argued that there was no systematic pattern between the two policies variables during other period while there are some forms of accommodativeness between the two policies from 1998-2008.

He concludes that the two policies have weak strategies.³² It is in that regard that Bodurin opines that both monetary and fiscal policy has not been able to address the challenges facing developing countries in matter of stability and structural transformation.³³

On the other hand, Alabi and Olarinde in their research proclaimed that Nigeria experienced a period of sustainable economic growth because prudent monetary and fiscal policy was applied in 2000-2006.³⁴ Thomas contends that past fiscal policy in Nigeria has not been successful since both revenue and expenditure have been highly volatile. He emphasized further that Nigeria faces two challenges when formulating fiscal policy. Firstly, there is need to ensure that the fiscal stance is compatible with the sustainable use of oil and gas recourses and secondly, there is need to prevent the revenue volatility from spilling over into the budget.³⁵ Also, Salisu and Saibu in their findings posited that several empirical studies have shown that none of the two policies can be accorded being superior than the other and their relative impact in any economy depends on the economic and political situation obtainable at a given period of time.³⁶ This is why Nwaogwugwu postulated that Nigerian economy is volatile due to its dependence on oil revenue and experiences instability through rising inflation, massive employment, low output, dwindling forcing reserves, leading to unstable exchange rates and other economic uncertainties.³⁷

From the foregoing, Nigeria did not fare well in both policies. It is either we have failed both system or both of them failed us. Nevertheless, democracy in Africa, particularly Nigeria is no longer the government of the people, by the people and for the people. Instead, it has become the government of the few and for the few.³⁸ The fiscal deficit arises mainly from the inequality between the government revenue and its expenditure, hence, Nigeria has always been having deficit budget except in some years.³⁹ For Nigeria to break free from the current economic retrogression, different scholars postulate varieties of opinion. We shall interrogate the dichotomy of the status quo and phenomenon.

Interrogating the Dichotomy

In the view of some economists, the policies adopted by government stifle the growth of private sector and no foreign direct investment will be interested in a society where insecurity has become the order of the day. They attributed it to why twenty-four States in Nigeria lost foreign investment in the year 2021. The analysis of figure released by the National Bureau of Statistic show that Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) had been fluctuating from 2012-2022. The latest capital importation report from (NBS) show that (FDI) fell by \$332 million in 2021 from \$1.028 billion in 2020.⁴⁰ Francis Ogbimi in this regard posits that promoting industrialization will arrest mass unemployment because it is the primary basis of economic democracy. Coupled with the fact that, industrialization can only be achieved through learning, application of theoretical science and research.⁴¹ Babatope argues that the reason why new generation graduates are unemployed is due to their educational career that was built on a faulty foundation. Graduates in twenty-first century are not marketable in the global economy. Thus, graduates are not only unemployed but unemployable as their skills are largely divorced from labour requirement. In 2014, 526,000 Nigerian jobless graduates stormed various recruitment centres to apply for 4,000 advertised vacant positions in the Nigerian Immigration Service. At least 16 people were reportedly died in the ensuing stampede.⁴²

On the other hand, Alexander *et al* contend that the accelerated growth of population on Nigeria's unemployment problem is multifaceted as it affects the supply side through high and rapid increase in labour force relative to the absorptive capacity of the economy. They insinuated that Nigeria should borrow a leaf from countries like China and India who practice with control policies to checkmate the production of children.⁴³ In our humble opinion, the question of population growth has a number of Islamic dimensions; economic, social, political and moral. The fact is that, when a national policy of birth control is likely to have serious harmful effect on the community as a whole, it is not permissible in Islam but this should not prevent a nation like Nigeria from keeping its citizens informed about the harmful consequence of poverty, malnutrition and disease on children whose parents are too poor to support a family. At the

national level what is important is to create an awareness of the problem of over and under-population so that an individual takes a responsible attitude toward this problem to accomplish his family needs.⁴⁴

In the Nigeria context, in the year past, when a father was said to be rich, it was only because he had many children who constitute the work force in the family. Thus, children were considered as wealth,⁴⁵ the rhetoric question here is why are children in the twenty-first century turn to be a contributing factor to poverty? It is in this regard that Asien opine that the zero million people in Nigeria is an opportunity which attract production and demand from the entire nation. He argues that benefits of population to trade and agriculture to beyond the traditional macro-economic policies and the goal of achieving stability. Asien asserts that the best option is to rely on our own resources which are agriculture, oil and gas.⁴⁶

Some scholars contend with the acclaimed practice of the advanced market economy. They urged government to redefine its own market economy from past and present realities because all countries have different mutual historical conditions and they face different contemporary challenges. They conclude that the previous policy makers were less pragmatic and that led Nigeria to where it is today.⁴⁷ Sodimu and others corroborate Asien that agro-forestry is a viable option for poverty alleviation in Nigeria for the fact that both monetary and fiscal policy seem to be short-term measures taken to address the issue of poverty and unemployment in Nigeria.⁴⁸ In our humble perspective, there is a popular poem in various schools in Yorubaland, Southwest Nigeria⁴⁹ which consider the significance of farming with formal education thus:

*Ise Agbe ni Ise Ilewa, Eni ko sise amajale, Iwe kiko lai si
oko ati ada, ko ipe oo, ko ipee oo !!!*

Translation:

*Farming is the major profession of our land,
Whoever fail to work will surely steal,
Education without farming tools, is incomplete!!!*

The import of the above poem reveals the relevant of skill in farming under western education in the educational system. It is crystal clear that reasons for high unemployment in Nigeria identified by various researchers are quite axiomatic. However, this work needs to highlight the management of monetary and fiscal policy in the macro-economic growth of Nigeria to curb inflation and unemployment.

Management of Monetary Policy: A Case Study of Early History of Islam

The place of Nigeria in the global economy has become an issue of policy relevance as a result of the rapid integration of the world's goods service and financial markets. In the drive to achieve accelerated economic growth, the Nigeria government has applied various models of economic management. In the perspective of Olaleye, Nigeria has operated two main regimes of economic management. These are the control and market system. The control regime was in place between 1960 and 1985 with the development plans as the major blueprint for stimulating the various sector of the economy toward the desired targets.⁵⁰

The above assertion was corroborated by Obadia when he articulates that the history of planning in Nigeria goes back to colonial times. In his own view, one of the popular delusions in our national economic management is that Nigeria's developmental planning is faulty because since then what Nigeria has called rolling plan and mid-term expenditure frameworks.⁵¹ The inability of trade and exchange controls to ensure internal balance and external sector viability resulted in the change management strategy in 1986 when the market system was embraced through the SAP. Under the SAP, liberalization and deregulation were the main policy thrusts to restructure the economy away from undue dependence on the oil sector.

In 1994, the control policy was re-introduced, notwithstanding Nigeria fashioned its macro-economic policies in the direction of other countries in its drive to open up its economy. The growth rate of the economy shows that openness has not contributed much to economic growth in Nigeria. Monetary and fiscal policies have been complementary under guided deregulation. Monetary policy has been combined and remained dominant against fiscal policy from 1960-1990; but from 1990 till date, it has been fiscal dominance which has undermine the efficacy of monetary policy. Hence, the need to fine-tune the fiscal policy to be more effective in addressing unemployment challenge.⁵² Reviving the Nigerian economy which is contending with stagnation, low Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth, high level of debt and fiscal deficit and restrictive monetary policy is indeed a complex and challenging task.

Management of Economy System in Islam

An Islamic economy uses its fiscal tools to achieve the desire economic objectives as stated at the beginning of this study. In order to curb inflation, achieve full employment and mobilize savings to accelerate economic growth, there is a great necessity to examine the mix of fiscal and monetary tools available in an Islamic economy.⁵³

- i. **Policy Mix under Macro-Economic Growth:** Islam does provide scope for securing a policy mix of monetary and fiscal policy which will permit the achievement of more objectives that would be possible with the use of one policy instrument alone.⁵⁴
- ii. **Management of Monetary through Curbing Inflation and Unemployment:** In non-Islamic free market, economy demand-pull inflation can originate in the monetary sector, while cost-push inflation results from imperfections in either labour market or product market. In a closed Islamic economy, demand-pull inflation is more likely to take place than cost-push inflation. This however, does not mean that trade unions cannot exist in an Islamic framework. It only indicates that in a such framework, harmony is brought about through a social contract reached between the employers and the employees in order to avoid social exploitation.⁵⁵

There are two cures for inflation in Islam. The first is through an increase in the rates of dues on personal incomes. This will result in a decline in consumption which will cause a shift in aggregate demand towards the equilibrium price level. The second method is to make use of the reserves accumulated in Government revenue. During the inflationary periods, the government could spend less than its reserves from full employment proceeds. This would result in a high degree of economic stability.⁵⁶ Today, many governments around the world generate inflationary condition by continuously increasing their expenditure, especially outlays related to security and expenditure on salaries of officials. This clearly contradicts constraint laid down by Islam on how public money should be spent.⁵⁷ It was reported that Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) says: *Who takes even a needle from public money will be accountable for it on the Day of Judgment.*⁵⁸

Abubakar, the first *Khalīf* (successor) after the demise of the Prophet told Aishah (his daughter), the Prophet's wife at the time of his death to hand over to Umar whatever was left in his house from government's reserve. The orthodox *Khalafāu* (successors) saw themselves as trustees of public money.⁵⁹ However, to finance their growing expenditure, many governments resort to taxes consumption which are price inelastic, hence adding to the inflationary spiral. Practical experience under macro-economic growth shows that interest is the root cause of the massive problem associated with both monetary and fiscal policy; to free the economy from inflation it must be freed from dominance of interest. Therefore, the economy that fails to ban interest will always face the music of inflation.⁶⁰ Government that aims at free the economy from inflation may reduce the previously agreed

interest rate (by legislative means) to the extent inflation is controlled or government may adopt dual currency system. The depreciating fiat money to be used (as unit of account) in transaction that involve interest and a standard currency.⁶¹ From our own point of view, reduction in inflation can be achieved if domestic production is encouraged for the fact that production should be considered as a major source of revenue because tax like saving is a derivative of revenue itself which itself is derived from production. Inflation in Nigeria is not demand-pull but cost push.⁶²

For the CBN to continue to raise interest rates with the hope that it will encourage saving is like taxing producers. This happens when the currency is tradable or a key currency, Naira is not in that category. The monetary authority opines that there is too much money in the hands of the citizens which is a contributing factor to inflation. The fact remains that the money is in the hands of certain people who fail to deposit such money in the banks. Nigeria policy makers need to search out for factors contributing to such phenomenon and apply policy that can curb it rather than relying on instructions from the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund (IMF). In an Islamic economy, the aggregate demand curve intersects the aggregate supply curve at a point which corresponds to a level of employment less than that of full employment. This would occur if investment is not sufficient to close the gap between national income and consumption expenditure. In the other hands, if there is a short fall of investment for securing full employment, Islam enjoins the government to stimulate aggregate demand by raising the rate of dues on idle assets, such as cash reserve, ratio, liquidity ratio, credit ceiling, and holding of cash.

This method would stimulate private investment and if the rate on dues on idle assets were higher than expected rate of loss on investment, more investment would be forthcoming.⁶³ It would also encourage consumption expenditure and contribute towards closing the gap between income and consumption. Hence, an increase in the rate of dues on idle assets would result in an increase in aggregate demand until full employment is accomplished.⁶⁴ The use of dues on idles assets in an Islamic economy to solve problems of unemployment during severe depressions is more effective than the use of expansionary fiscal policy which is an increase in government expenditure because it will result in the price level which would trigger the real money supply to decrease. The decrease in money supply will cause the rate of interest to rise and this will cause investment to fall. The net expansionary effect of the increase in government spending will therefore be reduced. Thus, instead of producing economic stability, the policy results in a greater instability.⁶⁵

In the modern world economy, it is either you have a balanced budget, budget surplus or budget deficit. In the polity of Nigeria, deficit budget has become the order of the day. This according to Subair (2006) do not yield the cost of production lets alone profit.⁶⁶ However, having deficit budget to finance capital projects increase employment opportunities which further generate income. As long as the income is spent, there will be an expansion of the economy.

However, Nigeria as a case study, the reverse has always been the case, due to increase in imported consumer goods. Subair articulates further that, the inability of monetary authority to ascertain the amount of money in circulation precisely renders the monetary policies ineffective.⁶⁷ This was attributed to poor record keeping, fake currencies, the habit of hoarding money and money doublers. The fiscal deficit arises mainly from the inequality between government revenue and its expenditure. The accumulation of debt which was reported to have started in 1978 to the tune of 37.1% as reported by the Debt Management Office (DMO) of Nigeria still persist.⁶⁸

The major defect of the Nigerian economy was attributed to her over-dependence on the export of one major commodity, fossil fuel and large-scale mismanagement.⁶⁹ Nigeria, like many other countries across the globe is left with three possible policy options for economic survival. The first is to drastically cut down on public expenditure. Unfortunately, both federal and state governments are not willing to do this. This fact is deduced from the lawmaker smiling home with an SUV vehicle

worth 160 million naira. Coupled with the renovation of the President's official residence with N4billion at Dodan Barracks Lagos, the approval of N1.6bn for vehicles for the first lady's Office when some 133 million Nigerians are multi-dimensionally poor.⁷⁰ Evidence to this reflects in the 2024 budget submitted to the National Assembly showed N28bn allocated to adorning government office.⁷¹ Therefore, there is a dire need for an augment between fiscal and monetary policies and fiscal and monetary discipline which have been a key failure factor of successive administration.

Management Of Promoting Nigeria Economy through Monetary and Fiscal Policies in Nigeria: Growth is a function of the rate of savings, fiscal and monetary policies with proper coordination and should aimed at achieving the maximum mobilization of savings in the economies, Fiscal policy in Islam aims at providing minimum necessities to its citizens and preventing huge accumulation of incomes and wealth is a few hands. The area of fiscal policy in Islam include: social welfare system, government expenditure policies, public enterprises operation, public debt and distributive policies of the government. Fiscal tools which were used effectively to achieve objectives of fiscal policy during the early history of Islam included taxes on land, *Zakāt* and other sources of permissible revenue.⁷² To ensure that monetary growth is adequate and not excessive, it would be important to monitor carefully three major sources of monetary expansion; these are financing of government budget deficit by borrowing from the CBN, expansion of deposits through commercial banks credit creation and monetization of the balance of payment.⁷³

Government and Citizen's Role in Management of Monetary Policy: Leadership as far as Islam is concerned is all about service.⁷⁴ This fact is embodied in a Prophetic tradition thus: *The leader of a people is their servant.*⁷⁵ The import of the above tradition is that everyone is a leader to the extent that one is able to serve and share one's ideas with others and make them realize it. This also suggests that leadership requires love and selfless service. The Qur'an warns Muslim against accumulation of wealth as part of *Jahiliyyah* practices⁷⁶ that have become a common phenomenon:

Woe unto every scander-monger and backbiter who piles with wealth thinking that his wealth would make him last forever. (Q. Al-Humazah, 104:1-4)

It is crystal clear that there is a gap between the injunction of Islam and Nigerian practices, particularly as it relates to how leadership was practiced. This gap is the embodiment of *Jahiliyyah* practices. Akolade (2022) posits that leadership in Islam is considered a trust and responsibility shows that leaders are required to meet their obligations to Allah as well as to discharge their duties towards their followers.⁷⁷ Islam as a complete way of life admonished the citizens on their responsibility to both the state and leadership as embodied in the following verse: *Oh you who believe, obey Allah the Messenger (of Allah) and those charged with authority among you. (Q. Al-Nisāi, 4:59)*

The above verse state clearly that obedience to those charged with authority. It is our submission here that thinking of leadership in terms of those who are privileged to govern the country alone can never solve the problem of indiscipline in both monetary and fiscal policy in Nigeria. Leadership does not start from the top; it is rather a matter of good home management and excellent upbringing of children.⁷⁸ Femi Abbas likened leadership to a pyramid which has a base rather than the apex.⁷⁹ This is why the following Yoruba adage is apt here:

Amukun eru e wo , Oni oke le now, e ewo Isale.

Translation:

A lame person was accused of his wrong arrangement of his load and her responds that people focus on the top rather than the base.⁸⁰

This simply means that, it will be unreasonable to start sighting major fault at the wall of a house when the foundation of the same house is evidently faulty. Accordingly, it was found that one-third of the population of western Nigeria evades taxes.⁸¹ Nanila in his own view argues that the private sector is taxed so much that there is no opportunity for the average business to prosper unless with connection.⁸² He articulates further that these taxes are in the form of side payments to all those committee area boys and check points that seem to have miraculously sprung up to supervise day-to-day business life.

Thus, while the official tax burden may be low once we factor in all the bribes and other impediments to business, the burden that entrepreneurs have to shoulder is considerable.⁸³ He concluded that, before Government turn to raising tax revenue, it must seek to lift all boats by preventing this petty thievery across the board that make Nigeria a place to run any kind of business without connection.⁸⁴ Some scholars opined in this regard that if the big businesses and corporations pay the appropriate taxes, the citizens are enlightened about their payments and the government is delivering dividends, it is easier to make individual, nano, small, and medium-scale enterprises (NSME) pay taxes.⁸⁵

This implies that transparency and accountability are factors for raising revenue from tax. This is why it is pertinent for the government to review the tax and monetary and fiscal policy in order to increase the ratio of revenue to GDP from less than 10 percent which is currently 18 percent. After life, security, law and justice, nothing else is held sacrosanct in Islam than governance. There is no gain saying in the fact that governance is centered on process, procedure and people. The failure of one of the three pillars will automatically cause instability of economic growth in Nigeria.

In this regard, both leadership and followership have definite roles to play as essential factors for economic growth and national development. What we have experienced and are experiencing and may continue to experience is not a cash flow or liquidity problem but a management crisis which is the bane of coordinating fiscal and monetary policy in Nigeria. National economic policies are design to enhance productivity and foster capital accumulation overtime. When the effects of these economic policies are weakened, productivity and capital accumulation are completely thwarted.⁸⁶

Findings of the Study

From a Yoruba adage, we learnt that “*when a kid suddenly slips and falls down, he looks forward to someone who can lift him up. But when an adult slips and falls down, he looks backward to see the causes of his fall.*”⁸⁷ It is in the light of this that some findings were discovered during the course of our research thus:

- i. Inflation in Nigeria is not demand pull but cost push.
- ii. Nigerian government generates inflationary condition through increment of expenditure.
- iii. Lack of adequate check and balance, mismanagement and bad governance are major factors contributing to accumulation of debt in Nigeria economy.
- iv. Fiscal deficit was caused to inequality between government revenue and expenditure.
- v. Hoarding of money, fake currencies and money doublers are challenges of monetary policy in Nigeria.
- vi. Absence of alignment of monetary and fiscal policy between monetary and fiscal discipline is a key failure factors for previous governance to manage macro economy.
- vii. Heavy dependence on the export of one major commodity; fossil fuel is a major defect of the Nigerian economy.
- viii. It was found that one third of the population of Western Nigeria evades taxes.
- ix. Over burden of taxes is a hindrance to small scale and other business growth.

- x. Interest loan in Nigeria economy always create inflation and instability.
- xi. Wasteful and consumption pattern of governance in Nigeria are inimical to the management of both monetary and fiscal policy in Nigeria.
- xii. The current fiscal and business policies in Nigeria is not *Sharī'ah*-compliant.

Recommendations

Based on the aforementioned findings of the study, the following are suggested:

- i. To curtail the rising domestic prices/inflation, government should ensure effective coordination of both monetary and fiscal policy measures.
- ii. Complete diversification of the economy is needed through adequate infrastructure.
- iii. Transparency and accountability are quite needed to motivate citizens to pay tax.
- iv. Productivity should be considered a major revenue for macro-economy in Nigeria.
- v. Quintessential leadership is a major factor in management of both monetary and fiscal policy.
- vi. Alignment between fiscal policy and fiscal discipline will engender stability in the economy.
- vii. Government support and a conducive regulatory framework are critical for the success of sustainable finance in Nigeria.
- viii. Stability of electricity supply, regional railway system and establishment of common refinery are three essential infrastructures to maintain multinational companies in Nigeria and creating opportunity for the middle class because no economy can thrive without them.
- ix. Government should adopt dual currency system (depreciating fiat money and standard currency) to reduce dominance of interest rate to cause massive problem for both monetary and fiscal policy.
- x. Strategic solution to economic crunch in Nigeria includes promoting massive employment windows, activating microeconomic components, establishing hotspots driven by organic and competitive private sector growth among others.

Conclusion

This interaction between monetary and fiscal policy in management and macro-economic in Nigeria can be deduced from the foregoing. This study investigates the basic difference between monetary and fiscal policy in Islamic economic and non-Islamic economics. It is crystal clear that there are substantial differences in the role of fiscal and monetary policies, their objectives, measures and mechanism in the two types of economies.

The study determines how both monetary and fiscal policy can be used to achieve equilibrium in the money market without interest. The paper tackles problems of inflation and unemployment in Islamic economy through manipulation of dues on incomes and idle assets. The findings of the study have policy implications for Islamic economies. The article suggests a methodology for budgeting in government to achieve economic stability. Islam provides scope for securing a policy mix of monetary and fiscal policy which allows the achievement of more objectives than the use of one policy instrument alone. We therefore conclude with a prophetic tradition thus: "*Moderation in spending is half of livelihood*".

Endnotes

¹M.A. Mannan, *Economic Development and Social Peace in Islam* (Bangladesh: Taha Publishers Ltd., 1989), 56.

²*Business Day*, "Unemployment: NBS Shouldn't Ruin Its Reputation," August 28, 2023, 12.

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